

Experimental

A methanolic solution of salicylaldehyde (0.61 g, 0.005 mol ; 10 cm³) was added dropwise to a hot methanolic solution of dihydralazine sulphate (1.44 g, 0.005 mol ; 10 cm³). The resulting yellow solid was washed with water and methanol, purified with the help of preparative tlc, recrystallised from hot methanol and dried over silica gel under reduced pressure, m.p. (uncorrected) 186° (Found : N, 29.02. C₁₅H₁₄N₆O requires : N, 28.67%).

The methanolic solution of metal (Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}) acetate (0.004 mol in 25 cm³) was refluxed with the methanolic solution of the Schiff base (0.008 mol in 25 cm³) on a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solid complex was washed with water and methanol, and dried over silica gel. By elemental analysis, the complexes were found to be M(C₁₅H₁₃N₆O)₂·2H₂O, where M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (Found : Co, 8.42 ; N, 24.94. Requires : Co, 8.63 ; N, 24.60%), (Found : Ni, 8.65 ; N, 24.70. Requires : Ni, 8.60 ; N, 24.61%) and (Found : Cu, 9.81 ; N, 24.40. Requires : Cu, 9.24 ; N, 24.63%).

Spectral Studies of some New Biologically Active Compounds

SANTOSH K. TALWAR*

Central Indian Pharmacopoeia Laboratory,
Ghaziabad-201 002

V. K. RASTOGI

Department of Physics, Lajpat Rai College,
Sahibabad-201 005

and

R. C. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, M. M. College,
Modi Nagar-201 204

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DIHYDRALAZINE (1,4-hydrazinophthalazine) is used for the treatment of hypertension of pregnancy¹. It has recently been revealed that the metallic complexes are more potent and less toxic in many cases as compared to the parent compound².

In view of the above, a new compound dihydralazine salicylaldehyde (DHS ; LH)

has been prepared and its complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been synthesised. Their structures have been established based on elemental analyses, electronic, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. The microbiological activity of dihydralazine salicylaldehyde and its metal complexes with *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* have also been studied.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analysis of the complexes indicate 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio. The metal complexes are insoluble in water and other non-coordinating organic solvents, but are soluble in DMF, dioxane and DMSO.

The electronic spectra of dihydralazine salicylaldehyde in dioxane show strong band at ≈40 000 and shoulder at ≈35 000 assignable to π-π* and n-π* transitions, respectively. These bands are retained in the complexes but show a blue-shift as compared to the ligand. The electronic spectra of the cobalt complexes show spin-allowed transitions at 16 000 and 22 988 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴A_{2g}(F) ← ⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(P) ← ⁴T_{1g}(F) transitions, respectively. The calculated spectral parameters like B (940 cm⁻¹), 10Dq (12 771 cm⁻¹), and β₃₅ (0.84) suggest octahedral geometry^{3,4}. Similarly, the nickel complex which demonstrates the presence of orbitals corresponding to d_{xy}, d_{x²-y²}, d_{z²} and d_{x²-y²} in which d_{x²-y²} is empty. The octahedral geometry indicating three spin-allowed transitions, 12 903, 17 100 and 22 222 cm⁻¹ assignable to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) are present in the synthesised complex^{5,6}. The spectral parameters of the Ni^{II} complex such as B (1 069 cm⁻¹), 10Dq (10 474 cm⁻¹), β₃₅ (0.99) also support O_h symmetry. The Cu^{II} complex shows a broad band at 14 705 cm⁻¹ indicating a D_{4h} symmetry⁶. A band occurring at 25 316 cm⁻¹ in the copper complex is a subject of controversy. Whereas Tsuchida and Yamada⁷ assumed this due to Cu-Cu linkage, Basu *et al.*⁸ referred this on account of d-d transitions but Graddon⁹ assumed it due to d_{xy} → d_{x²-y²}.

The ir spectra of dihydralazine sulphate (in KBr) reveal peaks at 1 600, 1 650, 3 310 and 3 440 cm⁻¹.

The peaks at 3 440 and 1 650 cm^{-1} can be assigned to NH asym and bending NH vibrations respectively, the peak of medium intensity at 3 310 cm^{-1} due to NHNH_2 group and the one at 1 600 cm^{-1} can tentatively be assigned to stretching aromatic vibration at $\text{C}=\text{N}^{10,11}$. The Schiff base shows the presence of two ir bands at 3 040 (bonded OH) and 1 400 cm^{-1} (OH)^{12,13}. A downward shift in case of the Schiff base from 3 440 to 3 400 cm^{-1} in respect sym-NH vibration suggests its participation. The appearance of a strong band at 1 580 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group demonstrating the formation of Schiff base. A strong band at 1 625 cm^{-1} in the Schiff base can be attributed to bending NH_2 vibrations, which indicates the presence of free NH_2 group. The deprotonation of the Schiff base in the complex formation results in OH frequency shift (40–50 cm^{-1}) in the ir spectra of the complexes. The involvement of azomethine linkage $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ appearing at 1 600 cm^{-1} show shift to the extent of 5–10 cm^{-1} in the metal complex, which also suggests coordination of this group with the metal ion¹⁴. The shift of C–O (phenolic) band to higher frequency (by 10 cm^{-1}) is usually taken as an evidence of formation of a phenolic oxygen bridge^{15,16}. A band of weak to medium intensity corresponding to M–O is observed at $\sim 620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complex.

¹H nmr spectra of the Schiff base show prominent signal at δ 8.0 (azomethine linkage¹²) and 9.3 (phenolic). The carboxylic group of the solvent (CF_3COOH) exchange quite rapidly with protons of phenol to give single peak near δ 10.0. The broadening of this peak can be attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding between OH and NH^{16} . Proton spectra of the cobalt complex show high-field shift from δ 8.0 to 8.7 indicating the participation of azomethine group in coordination. The disappearance of phenolic group also supports the coordination through OH linkage of the Schiff base¹⁷.

The Schiff base and their metal complexes were studied for their antibacterial behaviour towards *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. It was found that the copper and cobalt complexes show stronger activity (zone of inhibition = 14.50 and 14.25 mm, respectively) than that of nickel (11.90 mm). However, a different behaviour is observed in case of antibacterial activity against *K. pneumoniae*—the nickel complex (14.90 mm) shows enhanced activity as compared to the copper and cobalt complexes (13.15 mm). The results support the earlier contention³ that metal complexes are more potent than the parent compound: zone of inhibition = 12.80 (*E. coli*); 13.50 mm (*K. pneumoniae*).

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